

New biotype of brown planthopper in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam

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Brown planthoppers damaged large areas of IR26, IR30, and TN73-2 (IR1561-228-3-3) early in 1977 in Tien Giang, An Giang, and Dong Thap, three provinces with the highest rice production in the Mekong Delta. To determine if they were new biotypes hoppers were field collected and tested in a glasshouse with two sets of varieties carrying genes *Bph 1* and *bph 2*.

Preliminary results showed that the brown planthopper populations damaged varieties carrying the *Bph 1* gene but did not attack varieties with the *bph 2* gene (see table). Subsequent tests were conducted to determine the host preference of nymphs and adults, nymphal survival and development, and longevity and fecundity of adults. IR32, IR36, and IR38 adversely affected the brown planthoppers. The insects showed no preference for those varieties for feeding, shelter, and oviposition. The

Reaction of varieties to brown planthoppers collected in Tien Giang, Dong Thap, and An Giang provinces in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam.^a University of Can Tho, Vietnam, Jan.–Mar 1977.

Variety	Grade of damage ^b	Nymphs that reached adult stage ^c (%)	Longevity of female ^d (days) Range	Mean
<i>Bph 1 gene</i>				
IR34	MS	54 b	–	–
TN73-2	S	64 bc	2–25	8.5 c
IR26	S	88 c	2–10	7.0 c
IR30	MS	74 c	6–25	13.5 d
<i>bph 2 gene</i>				
IR38	R	12 a	2– 8	4.2 a
IR32	R	22 a	2– 8	4.8 b
IR36	R	26 a	2– 6	3.4 ab
<i>Susceptible checks</i>				
Mudgo	S	62 bc	2–20	9.6 cd
TN1	S	70 c	10–20	13.3 d

^aThe experiments were conducted in a glasshouse. In a column, any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bThe data were recorded when all plants of the susceptible check variety were killed.

^cFifty insects were observed for each variety with 5 replications.

^dTen pairs of adults were observed for each variety with 10 replications.

varieties manifested antibiosis for nymphal development and longevity of adults. Additional studies are necessary on fecundity.

About 2,000 local varieties and hybrid lines in the germ plasm bank of the University of Can Tho are being screened for resistance to biotype 2.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Deep-water tour of Thailand, Burma, and India

H. D. Catling, *Deep Water Rice Pest Management Project, Bangladesh*; S. K. De Datta, B. S. Vergara, *International Rice Research Institute*; D. HilleRisLambers and B. R. Jackson, *Thai-IRRI Deep Water Rice Project, Thailand*

Scientists from the IRRI deep-water rice team visited Thailand, Burma, and India in August 1977. In Thailand many deep-water rice areas that would normally be under 1 m of water were still dry and many farmers had to reseed because of drought. In Burma the rains came late and farmers in the deep-water areas were just beginning to transplant. But in Howrah, West Bengal, India, heavy rains

Gathering samples for an insect survey in a farmer's field in West Bengal, India, are Dr. H. D. Catling of the Bangladesh Deep-Water Rice Pest Management Project (left) and Dr. Derk HilleRisLambers of the Thai-IRRI Deep-Water Rice Project.

damaged seedbeds and newly transplanted rice.

The Agricultural Research Institute at Yezin, Burma, has recently completed three ponds for screening deep-water rice. The International Rice Deep Water

Observational Nursery (IRDWON) will be planted in these ponds. At Patna, Bihar, India, nine new ponds, constructed in 1977, are being used to test the rice germ plasm.

In Burma, farmers are increasingly